

Niosome As A Promising Tool for Increasing the Effectiveness of Anti-Diabetic Drug for Vesicular Drug Delivery System

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ABSTRACT

Drug delivery systems are characterized as formulations designed for the transportation of a drug to the targeted area of action within the body. The fundamental element of drug delivery systems is a suitable carrier that safeguards therefrom swift degradation or elimination, consequently increasing drug concentration in targeted tissues. Niosomes are promising drug carriers due to their biodegradable, biocompatible, and nonimmunogenic structure, which are created through the self-association of nonionic surfactants and cholesterol in an aqueous environment. In recent years, many research articles have been published in scientific journals highlighting the potential of niosomes to act as carriers for the delivery of various types of drugs. This review outlines preparation methods, characterization techniques, and recent studies concerning niosomal drug delivery systems and provides current information regarding recent applications of niosomes in drug delivery.

Keywords: Niosomes, targeted drug delivery, Biocompatible

INTRODUCTION

Niosomes are biodegradable, biocompatible, harmless, and capable of encapsulating large volumes of material into relatively smaller vesicles. It can be predicted that encapsulation of the drug in a vesicular construct will prolong the presence of the drug in systemic circulation and thus enhance diffusion into the target material and reduce toxicity [1]. The minuscule non-ionic surfactant vesicles known as niosomes have spherical, unilamellar, bilayer, multilamellar, and polyhedded shapes [2]. Niosomes formed by hydration are tiny lamellar structures that arise from the combination of non-ionic surfactants from the alkyl or dialkyl polyglycerol ether category with cholesterol. Their structure, which includes hydrophilic, amphiphilic, and lipophilic components, allows them to encapsulate drug molecules with different solubility profiles [3]. Due to poor water

solubility, efflux by gut wall transporters, and first pass metabolism, oral administration of Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS) II drugs typically results in low and variable bioavailability. Numerous formulation techniques, including solid dispersions, Nano emulsions, Nano suspensions, and nanoparticles based on lipids and polymers have developed to get around these problems. Liposomes and niosomes share structural similarities [4]. Compared to widely utilized Nano systems, niosomes are potential nanocarriers with a number of benefits [5]. Niosomes represent a possibly effective method for delivering phytochemicals compounds, due to their limited solubility in bodily fluids. Different niosomes have been created to address the shortcomings of phytoconstituents [6]. Niosomes are stable against oxidation and hydrolysis processes, and hence, it improves the shelf life of the

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formulation [7]. In Niosomes, small size range of particles leads to high surface area available for drug absorption through the skin, and thereby provides greater efficacy. These nanocarriers help in formation of thin film on the skin and has occlusive effect with decrease in the [8]. For instance, the oral administration of repaglinide has faced criticism because of first pass metabolism, therefore

diminished bioavailability. The necessity for prolonged repaglinide delivery is additionally supported by the need to keep stable plasma levels for the effective long-term control of blood sugar in diabetic individuals. Under these circumstances, transdermal drug delivery continues to be the preferred method of administration [9].

Figure 1.1: Structure Of Niosomes

METHOD OF PREPARATION:

The formulation of niosomes requires a combination of lipids and surfactants, which are hydrated at elevated temperatures. Subsequently, a size-reduction process is conducted to create a colloidal suspension. Several techniques utilized for the preparation of niosomes include the handshaking/thin-film hydration method, ether injection, microfluidization, and sonication. The handshaking/thin-film hydration method specifically entails dissolving surfactants and cholesterol in an organic solvent to produce niosomes [10].

1. Hand Shaking / Thin-Film Hydration Method:

In this method, surfactants and additional additives are uniformly dissolved in an organic solvent, such as chloroform or a combination of organic solvents, within a round-bottom flask. Subsequently, the solvent is entirely removed using a rotary vacuum evaporator, resulting in a thin film adhering to the inner surface of the flask. This thin film is then rehydrated with an aqueous medium, which may consist of water or phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) that typically contains the drug intended for encapsulation. Upon completion of the rehydration process, niosomes of varying diameters are produced.

2. Solvent Injection Method:

In this method, solvents like diethyl ether and ethanol are employed to dissolve surfactants and various additives. This homogeneous solution is subsequently transferred into a syringe pump, from which it is injected drop-wise through a needle into an aqueous solution maintained at a constant temperature exceeding the boiling point of the organic solvent. The residual organic solvent is entirely removed using a rotary vacuum evaporator. Throughout this evaporation process, unilamellar vesicular niosomes of varying sizes are formed, with a relatively greater entrapped aqueous volume compared to other techniques.

3. Bubble Method:

In the bubble method, niosomes are synthesized without the use of organic solvents. Surfactants and additives are combined in an aqueous medium, such as phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), and subsequently transferred to a three-neck round-bottom flask. This flask is then placed in a water bath to regulate the temperature. The dispersion of surfactants and additives occurs at a temperature of 70 °C. Initially, a high shear homogenizer is employed to achieve homogeneous dispersion by stirring for a duration of 15 to 30 seconds, after which nitrogen gas is bubbled through the solution at 70 °C [11].

Figure 2: Bubble Method

4. Slurry Method:

In this method, the carbohydrate carriers are loaded into the round bottom flask. Then the lipid components are dissolved in ethanol separately. Then these are directly infused into the carbohydrate carriers to form a slurry. The flask holding the alcoholic slurry is connected to the rotary evaporator and partially submerged in a water bath maintained at 45 °C. This setup facilitated the evaporation of ethanol through rotation and reduced pressure over a

duration of 2 hours. Subsequently, the flask is positioned under the fume hood for an overnight period [12].

5. Sonication Method:

In this method, the lipid components are heated on a water bath at 60 °C until uniformity is achieved. Then drug and aqueous solvent is heated on a water bath at 60 °C. Then these mixtures are mixed with continuous stirring and finally it is subjected to probe sonication for about 5 minutes to form niosomes [13].

Figure 3: Probe Sonicator

6. Reverse Ethanol Injection Method:

The precise weights of Repaglinide, PhosphatidylCholine, Cholesterol, and Span 60 were dissolved in 2 mL of ethanol. A suitable quantity of preheated distilled water (at 60 °C), with or without Tween 80, was slowly added to the lipid solution in ethanol while stirring continuously with a magnetic stirrer. The stirring process was maintained at room temperature for 1 hour to ensure that all the ethanol was completely removed. This dispersion was subjected to sonication at room temperature for 10 minutes using a bath sonicator. Subsequently, this mixture was stored overnight in a refrigerator to allow the lipo niosomal hybrids to mature fully [14].

7. Solvent Diffusion Method:

In molten form, 1.75 ml of surfactant (GMO) was used to dissolve 100 mg of quercetin. Following this, 12.5 ml of a 0.1% copolymer (poloxamer 188) was added gradually, and the mixture was sonicated for 3 minutes at a power of 18 W. To create the final nanoemulsion, a 2.4% solution of Eudragit S100 was incorporated into the initial emulsion. The resulting product was subjected to freeze-drying for 48 hours with percent mannitol serving as the cryoprotectant, resulting in a fine nanoparticle powder. The produced whitish lyophilized product was collected and stored at 4°C until required [15].

APPLICATIONS OF NIOSOMES

- Niosomal spreading in an aqueous segment can be mixed in a non-aqueous stage to administer the typical vesicle in external non-aqueous environment and regulate the medication's distribution rate.
- The vehicle suspension system is water-based. This suggests excellent patient compliance when using greasy dose forms for evaluation.
- Niosomes can hold drug particles with a variety of solubilities because of its infrastructure, which consists of hydrophilic, amphiphilic, and lipophilic molecules together. The vesicle preparation's characteristics are controllable and scalable.
- The vesicles can act as a reservoir, releasing the medication in a regulated manner.

- They possess osmotic energy and stability, and they enhance the reliability of encapsulated drugs.
- They enhance the oral bioavailability of medications that are poorly absorbed and boost the skin penetration of drugs.
- They can effectively distribute the site of action via oral, parenteral, and topical methods.
- The surfactants are recyclable, biocompatible, and non-immunogenic, making them safe for the formulation of Niosomes.[1]

LITERATURE REVIEW

Table:1.1

S.No	Name Of The Drug	Method Of Preparation	Title	Conclusion	Reference
1.	Glimepiride	Solvent evaporation method	Formulation and evaluation of glimepiride loaded niosomes by applying multiple membrane extrusion techniques by using various non-ionic surfactants.	Glimepiride-loaded niosomes showed acceptable drug content and entrapment efficiency. The multiple membrane extrusion method effectively minimized drug leakage, and the use of Span-40, Span-60, and Span-80 improved the stability of the niosomes.	[1]
2.	Glibenclamide	Modified ether injection technique	Formulation and pharmacodynamics evaluation of glibenclamide incorporated niosomal gel.	Glibenclamide was successfully incorporated into niosomes using a modified ether injection method, resulting in a gel with prolonged and controlled drug release compared to plain glibenclamide gel. The transdermal delivery system effectively reduced blood glucose levels while minimizing side effects like gastric disturbances and anorexia, improving patient compliance. These findings were supported by in vitro permeation and in vivopharmacodynamic studies in diabetic rats, with potential for future application in humans.	[2]

3.	Repaglinide	Thin film hydration method	The Impact of Surfactant Composition and Surface Charge of Niosomes on the Oral Absorption of Repaglinide as a BCS II Model Drug.	The study concludes that Tween 80-based niosomes, especially with a positive surface charge, significantly enhance the oral bioavailability of REG, a BCS II drug, compared to conventional drug suspension. This formulation could serve as a promising platform for the oral delivery of BCS II drugs, providing an alternative and effective method for improving their bioavailability.	[4]
4.	Curcumin	Thin film hydration method	Optimization of curcumin loaded niosomes for drug delivery applications	A three-level Box-Behnken design was used to optimize CUR-loaded niosome nanoparticles, which demonstrated stability at 5–40°C for up to two months. Optimized formulations showed sustained drug release, with an initial rapid release due to surface-bound drug molecules on the niosomes.	[5]
5.	Plumbagin	Thin film hydration method	Formulation and Evaluation of Plumbagin-Loaded Niosomes for an Antidiabetic Study: Optimization and In Vitro Evaluation.	In conclusion, it was determined that plumbagin-loaded niosomes are a more effective form of delivery of plumbagin and a better strategy for managing diabetes mellitus. The Improved Plumbagin Niosomes demonstrated good stability and sustained release.	[6]
6.	Glipizide	Thin film hydration method	Hydrogen bonded niosomes for encapsulation and release of hydrophilic and hydrophobic anti-diabetic drugs: An efficient system for oral anti-diabetic formulation.	A niosomal formulation encapsulating glipizide and metformin HCl was developed for diabetes treatment. Spherical niosomes (230 ± 50 nm) were formed by self-assembly of Tween 80 and cholesterol. Structural stability was enhanced by hydrogen bonding between cholesterol's hydroxyl groups and Tween 80's carbonyl groups.	[7]
7.	Pioglitazone	Thin film hydration method	Nanostructured lipid carriers of pioglitazone for transdermal application: from experimental design to	NLC formulations were able to efficiently encapsulate PZ, and provide a reservoir system for long-term administration. The result showed enhanced skin transport (3.2 times) compare to control formulation with high loading (10.41%). The pharmacokinetic study showed 2.17 times enhanced bioavailability in	[8]

			bioactivity detail.	compare to oral tablet. The antidiabetic study showed that NLCs controlled blood sugar levels for 48 h.	
8.	Repaglinide	—	A study on ethosomes as mode for transdermal delivery of an antidiabetic drug.	Repaglinide can be successfully delivered through skin for the treatment of type II diabetes mellitus. Ethosomal RPG delivery is capable of prolonging drug release that might reduce the dosage frequency.	[9]
9.	Gliclazide	Sonication	Bioavailability and Antidiabetic Activity of Gliclazide-Loaded Cubosomal Nanoparticles.	Gliclazide-loaded cubosomal nanoparticles, prepared with GMO and P407, showed high drug entrapment (80%) and enhanced drug release compared to gliclazide suspension. In rats, the cubosome formulation improved drug absorption, increasing bioavailability and glucose reduction. These findings suggest cubosomal nanoparticles as a promising carrier for enhancing gliclazide's oral bioavailability and hypoglycemic effect, though further stability studies are needed.	[13]
10.	Repaglinide	Solvent diffusion method	Bioavailability enhancement of repaglinide using nano lipid carrier: Preparation characterization and in vivo evaluation.	Repaglinide-loaded SLN and NLC dispersions were developed with high drug entrapment, using a modified solvent diffusion process. NLCs showed smaller particle sizes and higher entrapment compared to SLNs. Both formulations exhibited good physical stability and sustained, biphasic drug release, following Higuchi diffusion kinetics. In vivo studies confirmed the potential of repaglinide-loaded nanodispersions as effective nanocarriers for diabetes treatment.	[25]
11.	Glibenclamide	Slurry method	Formulation of Glibenclamide proniosomes for oral administration: Pharmaceutical and pharmacodynamics evaluation.	The vesicular proniosomal formulation for GB was considered one of the most successful methods in enhancing the dissolution rate of the drugs. This simple and easy process produced vesicular particles with nanosize and good stability. The pharmacological activity of GB pro-niosomal formulation showed a significant improvement compared with pure drugs.	[21]

12.	Glimepiride	Nanoemulsion-Based Gel Method	Glimepiride-Loaded Nanoemulgel; Development, In Vitro Characterization, Ex Vivo Permeation and In Vivo Antidiabetic Evaluation.	This study successfully formulated nanoemulgel systems using clove oil, Tween 80, and PEG-400, addressing the poor transdermal bioavailability of glimepiride (GMP). The incorporation of solubility-enhance GMP/ β CD/GEL-44/16 significantly improved the in vitro release and skin absorption of GMP. Nanoemulgel based on GMP/ β CD/GEL-44/16 exhibited higher anti-diabetic activity compared to pure GMP-based nanoemulgel and marketed GMP. These findings suggest that enhanced solubility boosts bioavailability and that the combination of nanoemulsion and gel provides an effective carrier for GMP's topical delivery in rats.	[19]
14.	Vildagliptin	Nanoprecipitation Method or Chemical Precipitation and Drug Encapsulation	Fabrication of novel vildagliptin loaded ZnO nanoparticles for anti-diabetic activity.	In this study, ZnO nanoparticles (NPs) were synthesized and loaded with the anti-diabetic drug Vildagliptin to improve its efficacy. The nanoparticles were characterized by UV-Visible spectroscopy, which confirmed the successful synthesis, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) revealed a flaky texture. The Freundlich isotherm model indicated efficient drug adsorption. The drug-loaded ZnO NPs exhibited enhanced anti-diabetic activity, showing both α -amylase and DPP-IV inhibition, with maximum inhibitory effects observed at 1000 μ g/ml. This suggests a synergistic effect of the ZnO NPs and Vildagliptin, enhancing the drug's overall efficacy.	[17]
17.	Insulin	Vesicular Emulgel System Preparation with Factorial Design	Vesicular Emulgel Based System for Transdermal Delivery of Insulin: Factorial Design and in Vivo Evaluation.	Insulin's transdermal absorption is challenging due to the skin's lipophilic stratum corneum. Combining niosomes with emulgel significantly enhances insulin absorption, showing the highest plasma glucose reduction among tested formulations. Further human studies are needed to optimize dosage and ensure individualized application. This novel niosome-emulgel system represents a promising noninvasive insulin delivery method, improving patient compliance.	[23]
19.	Quercetin	Solvent Evaporation Method	Evaluation of In-vitro Antidiabetic	Herbal formulations are favored over allopathic drugs due to fewer side effects, affordability, and safety. The	

			Activity of Quercetin Loaded Eudragit S100/GMO Nanoparticles.	study successfully synthesized stabilized quercetin-loaded nanoparticles, showing superior antidiabetic effects compared to metformin by inhibiting α -amylase and α -glucosidase and enhancing glucose uptake. FT-IR, DSC, and XRD analyses confirmed no interaction with Eudragit S100 polymer. Further in vitro and in vivo studies are needed to validate its antidiabetic potential and elucidate its mechanisms.	[15]
20.	Pioglitazone	Solvent casting method	Effective Therapeutic Delivery and Bioavailability Enhancement of Pioglitazone Using Drug in Adhesive Transdermal Patch.	The study developed a pioglitazone transdermal patch, optimized with Duro-Tak 87-2516 and propylene glycol, to enhance drug delivery for Type 2 diabetes. The patch showed improved transdermal flux and bioavailability in a rat model. The results suggest that transdermal therapy could be a promising alternative to oral delivery, but further human bioequivalence studies are needed.	[24]
22.	Solanum Xanthocarpum	Thin Film Hydration Method	In-vitro and ex-vivo antidiabetic, and antioxidant activities of Box-Behnken design optimized Solanum xanthocarpum extract loaded niosomes.	The study concludes that SXE-loaded niosomes represent an effective dosage form for the delivery of Solenostemma xanthocarpum extract, offering improved intestinal penetration, controlled release, and enhanced antidiabetic activity. This formulation could potentially be a better strategy for managing diabetes mellitus, providing an alternative approach to conventional therapies. The formulation also benefits from the use of the Box-Behnken design to optimize the niosomal characteristics, ensuring a high degree of formulation precision.	[16]
23.	Tradescantia pallida	High energy probe sonication method	Novel phyto niosomes formulation of Tradescantia pallida leaves attenuates Diabetes more effectively than pure extract.	Tradescantia pallida leaf extract-loaded niosomes can serve as a promising long-acting controlled release formulation for antidiabetic therapy. The niosomal formulation not only enhances the stability and bioavailability of the extract but also shows superior in vitro antidiabetic activity compared to acarbose. The presence of polyphenols in the extract plays a crucial role in the formulation's therapeutic effects. This approach could potentially lead to	[18]

				more effective and sustained management of diabetes.	
24.	Pioglitazone	QbD-Based Carbopol Transgel Formulation	QbD-based carbopol transgel formulation: characterization, pharmacokinetic assessment and therapeutic efficacy in diabetes.	and a Box–Behnken design. The formulation showed biphasic drug release, maintained effective plasma concentrations for 48 hours, and demonstrated prolonged blood sugar reduction compared to oral tablets, highlighting its potential to improve patient compliance and clinical outcomes.	[22]
25.	Repaglinide	Reverse ethanol injection method	Formulation of Deformable Lipo Niosomal Hybrid of Repaglinide: In vitro Characterization and Evaluation of the Anti-Diabetic Effect.	The study developed RPG-loaded LNHS using a 2 ³ factorial design and reverse ethanol injection technique. The optimized formulation (F7) improved RPG's solubility, permeability, bioavailability, and hypoglycemic effect, offering a robust drug delivery solution by integrating liposomes and niosomes.	[14]
26.	Gymnemic acid	Thin Film Hydration Method	Preparation, optimization and biological evaluation of gymnemic acid loaded niosomes against streptozotocin-nicotinamide induced diabetic-nephropathy in Wistar rats	GA-loaded niosomes were successfully prepared using a Box-Behnken design approach. The optimized GA-loaded niosomes formulation demonstrated vesicles size of 138.8 nm with zeta potential and entrapment efficiency of 76.9 mV and 87.5%, respectively.	
27.	Canagliflozin		Development and optimization of amphiphilic self-assembly into nanostructured liquid crystals for transdermal delivery of an antidiabetic SGLT2 inhibitor.	CFZ-NLCG2 succeeded in overcoming challenges of skin barrier and delivering the drug transdermally at therapeutic levels that could exert an antihyperglycemic activity equivalent to or even exceeding that obtained in the oral route. This study suggests that transdermal delivery of Canagliflozin using the developed NLCG system could be an effective and scalable alternative to oral administration, with the potential to reduce therapeutic doses and enhance selectivity for	

				renal SGLT, thereby improving patient outcomes.	
28.	Glibenclamide	Box- Behnken Design Optimization Method for Lipid-Based Nanoparticle Preparation	Application of Box–Behnken design for preparation of glibenclamide loaded lipid based nanoparticles: Optimization, in vitro skin permeation, drug release and in vivo pharmacokinetic study.	NLC of glibenclamide were prepared and optimized by employing Box–Behnken design approach. Prepared NLC showed reasonable particle size, entrapment efficiency, and showed potential skin permeation. Optimized NLC showed enhanced bioavailability of glibenclamide in Wistar rats. transdermal delivery of glibenclamide was significantly enhanced by optimized NLC.	[20]
29.	Glipizide	Thin Film Hydration Method	Formulation, Evaluation and Optimization of Glipizide loaded Niosomes.	Glipizide-loaded niosomes were spherical with a mean diameter of 451.6 nm. The optimized formulation (N6) showed high entrapment efficiency (82.3%) and sustained drug release (94.13% over 24 hours). Stability studies revealed faster degradation at room temperature, indicating that storage at 4°C is optimal. The study concludes that Glipizide-loaded niosomes offer a promising approach for type II diabetes treatment, emphasizing improved efficacy and patient compliance.	[3]

Evaluation Studies:

Entrapment Efficiency:

By employing the ultra-centrifugation technique, the percentage of entrapment efficiency was assessed. A centrifuge was utilized to spin a niosome sample at a designated concentration for one hour at 4 °C. Following appropriate dilution, the resulting supernatant was analyzed to check for free drugs, and quantification was performed using the formula:

$$\text{Entrapment Efficiency} = \frac{A1 - A2}{A1} \times 100$$

Where A1 represents the concentration of herbal drug used in the loaded niosomes, and A2 indicates the concentration of drug believed to be present in the supernatant [16].

In-Vitro Drug Release:

The anti-diabetic effect was assessed in vitro by measuring the inhibition of α -amylase and DPP IV

activity in the nanoparticles. The formulation achieved a peak inhibition of 82.06% for α -amylase and 94.73% for DPP IV, respectively [17].

Transmission Electron Microscope [TEM]:

The structure of niosomes was observed through TEM analysis. Samples were stained negatively with a 2% uranyl acetate solution. In addition to standard TEM analysis of the niosome samples, control niosome formulations were diluted further to prevent aggregation and to visualize individual particles. The samples were prepared using carbon-coated copper mesh and allowed to air dry at room temperature prior to measurements [18].

Zeta Potential:

Zeta potential is commonly used as a measure of a nanoemulsion system's stability. It is evident that increased stability is a result of higher zeta potential

levels. However, the literature shows a wide range of values from 1.5 to 45.5 mV, therefore these values cannot be used only to assess stability. The detected zeta potential values ranged from -12.8% to -20.7 mV and were all negative. Electrostatic repulsion occurs in nanoemulsions with negatively charged droplets, promoting free coalescence and preserving a well-dispersed emulsion system [19]. After evaluation, the drug nanolipid carriers' zeta potential was determined to be -31.0 ± 2.13 mV [20]. The proniosomal powders were hydrated with phosphate buffer at a pH of 7.4 and subjected to bath sonication for 10 minutes. Following appropriate dilution, the resulting dispersion was analyzed for size and zeta potential using a Malvern Zeta Sizer System, version 6.02 [21].

In-Vivo Permeation Studies:

The antidiabetic effects observed in vivo suggest that niosomes formulated gel delivered the medication steadily over an extended duration, leading to sustained regulation of blood sugar levels for up to 48 hours [22].

Scanning Electron Microscopy [Sem]:

The structure of niosome emulgel formulation was assessed through scanning electron microscopy. The niosome emulgel was mixed with water at a ratio of 1:10. A small number of sample drops were placed on a stub that was coated with double-sided adhesive tape and allowed to dry before further processing and covered in gold for clarity. The image obtained by using SEM shows tiny, spherical vesicles dispersed throughout the macromolecular polymer network. There were no noticeable insulin crystals in the formulation, suggesting that the drug was highly soluble [23].

Ex-Vivo Permeation Studies:

Diffusion through rat skin was measured with a vertical Franz diffusion cell for 12 hours. Excised skin membranes were mounted in diffusion cells with the dermal side down in contact with receptor fluid. The receptor fluid was phosphate buffer saline with 10% Tween 80, pH 7.4 (PBS-T). The skin surface area available for drug absorption was 0.64 cm². PBS-T was used in both donor (1 mL) and receptor (5 mL) compartments for pretest equilibrium. After this step, the fluid in the donor and receptor was withdrawn and a circular DIE patch was applied on the skin with light pressure to immobilize the device on the skin. The receptor compartment was filled with PBS-T. mixed at constant speed (600rpm) and maintained at a

temperature of 37 ± 0.5 °C using a circulating water bath. At certain time intervals, samples were collected and substituted with an equivalent volume of fresh PBS-T [24].

CONCLUSION:

In recent decades, nano and micro-sized vesicular drug delivery systems have attracted researchers' attention. Most studies concluded that vesicular drug delivery systems could increase the stability of drugs that are sensitive to environmental conditions or particularly could protect them in harsh conditions of the GI tract for oral drug delivery. In addition, vesicular systems can increase the absorption of drug molecules with low absorption properties. Niosomes, the type of vesicular delivery system, do it with non-ions and active surfacing, were first developed for cosmetic and industrial use. Therefore, these vesicle systems are attractive to many researchers. However, in the case of anti-inflammatory drugs that include chemical and natural compounds. They mainly have problems with absorption and also have serious AE. In the future, these compounds will have many applications in the field of targeted drug delivery, especially in cancer, from their physical and chemical properties and biological effects natural compounds. They mainly have problems with absorption and also have serious AE. In the future, these compounds will have many applications in the field of targeted drug delivery, especially in cancer, from their physical and chemical properties and biological effects. As this review were included antidiabetic drug as a vesicular drug delivery system in nearby future to minimize the oral medication and its adverse effects.

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